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**Comparative Study of Tomb Prayer in
African Traditional Religion and Christ
Apostolic Church in Southwestern
Nigeria**

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Abstract

Tomb prayer, which involves communication or symbolic interaction with deceased ancestors, is a central element of African Traditional Religion (ATR), reflecting the spiritual, cultural, and social significance of the living-dead relationship. In contrast, CAC emphasizes Christ-centered prayer, discouraging practices that resemble ancestral invocation to maintain doctrinal purity. This study explores tomb prayer practices in ATR and the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) in Southwestern Nigeria, focusing on theological responses and doctrinal implications. The study employed a qualitative research design, using purposive sampling to select forty participants, including pastors, theologians, elders, prayer leaders, and lay members from four venerated tombs of revered prophets in Christ Apostolic Church. The selected tombs are those of Apostle Joseph Ayodele Babalola, Prophet Timothy Obadare, Prophet Samson Oladeji Akande and Prophet Michael Ojo Olowere. The sacred space theoretical framework is used for this study. Data were collected through questionnaire and document analysis, and thematic analysis was applied to interpret the findings.

Results revealed a high level of engagement with tomb prayer among CAC members, demonstrating awareness of its doctrinal limitations. Nevertheless, some common features were identified, including symbolic reverence for the dead and commemorative visits to graves, indicating a cultural influence on Christian practice. The study also found that contextual theology provides a framework for moderating or reinterpreting tomb prayer practices, allowing cultural memory to be honored without compromising doctrinal integrity. The study concludes that tomb prayer in ATR and the CAC share similarities in purpose and theological meaning, although there are some differences. Recommendations include the implementation of contextual theology programs, doctrinal education, pastoral counseling, and development of alternative commemorative practices. This study contributes to understanding how African cultural practices intersect with Christian doctrine and offers insights for churches seeking to contextualize spirituality responsibly.

Keywords: Tomb Prayer, African Traditional Religion, Christ Apostolic Church, Contextual Theology, Doctrinal Implications, Cultural Heritage

Introduction

Tomb prayer in African Traditional Religion (ATR) is deeply rooted in the cultural, spiritual, and social fabric of African communities. In many traditional societies, the tombs of ancestors are not merely seen as physical resting places for the deceased but are considered sacred spaces that facilitate ongoing communication between the living and the spiritual world (Madukasi, 2021). This practice stems from the belief that ancestors remain active participants in the lives of their descendants, offering guidance, protection, and intervention in daily affairs (Ushe, 2017). The veneration of the saints among the Christians and the Ancestor worship among the adherents of African Traditional religion has been seen as a thing that is very sacrosanct in commemoration of both cults in the religious paradigm (Madukasi, 2021).

Rituals performed at tombs often include prayers, offerings, libations, chants, and symbolic gestures, all of which serve to maintain harmony between the living and the dead. Such practices underscore the communal and relational nature of African spirituality, where the living are never entirely separate from the ancestral presence (Adesanya, 2025). Recent studies have highlighted that even in contemporary African society, tomb prayer continues to influence moral behavior, decision-making, and social cohesion, demonstrating its enduring significance (Oyetayo & Afolaranmi, 2024). These rituals also provide a medium for cultural continuity,

transmitting values, history, and collective memory across generations, reinforcing identity and belonging within the community.

In contrast, the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC), a major Pentecostal and indigenous African church, negotiates these cultural practices within a Christian doctrinal framework. CAC emphasizes that prayer should be directed solely to God through Jesus Christ and maintains strict doctrinal opposition to any form of spirit invocation or necromancy (Afolarin, 2018). Despite this, anecdotal evidence and recent studies reveal that some members of CAC engage in practices resembling tomb prayer, such as praying at graves of deceased spiritual leaders or relatives (Taiwo, 2011). These practices reflect a complex negotiation between cultural heritage and Christian faith, illustrating the tension between inherited African spiritual traditions and the church's theological stance. Scholars note that this tension is not unique to CAC but is common across African Pentecostal and indigenous churches, which often struggle to balance cultural relevance with doctrinal fidelity (Anizoba, 2023). The church's ongoing struggle to clearly define acceptable practices underscores the need for theological reflection and contextual engagement, highlighting the importance of examining how tomb prayer has been adapted, modified, or resisted within Christian settings.

From a biblical perspective, tomb prayer raises doctrinal concerns. The Scriptures consistently warn against practices associated with consulting the dead. For instance, Deuteronomy 18:10–12 explicitly prohibits “anyone who consults the dead or practices divination,” labeling such practices as detestable in the sight of God. Similarly, the New Testament emphasizes that access to God is exclusively through Christ, the sole mediator between God and humanity (1 Timothy 2:5). This theological orientation challenges the legitimacy of tomb prayer within Christian contexts, particularly when it involves seeking spiritual intervention from the deceased rather than God. Critics argue that engaging in tomb prayer risks syncretism, where cultural practices are assimilated into Christian worship without critical theological assessment, potentially undermining doctrinal integrity (The Gospel Coalition Africa, 2025). The church, therefore, faces the critical task of distinguishing between culturally meaningful commemoration and practices that may inadvertently contravene biblical teaching.

Contextual theology offers a framework for addressing this tension, enabling churches to interpret and respond to cultural practices in ways

that are both culturally sensitive and theologically sound. Through contextual theology, practices like tomb prayer can be critically evaluated and, where appropriate, transformed into forms of remembrance and honor that align with Christian beliefs. For example, symbolic or memorial prayers may be conducted to celebrate the lives and legacies of deceased relatives or church leaders without invoking them as intermediaries. African theologians argue that such approaches respect cultural identity while maintaining doctrinal fidelity, demonstrating that not all engagement with ancestral traditions is inherently un-Christian (Mashabela, 2024). Recent scholarship highlights that contextual theology also encourages dialogue between church leaders and members, promoting understanding and gradual transformation of practices that might otherwise lead to syncretism or doctrinal compromise.

Furthermore, the comparative study of tomb prayer in ATR and CAC illuminates the broader intersection of culture and faith in African Christianity. While ATR views tombs as spiritually potent and interactive spaces, CAC must navigate the balance between honoring cultural heritage and upholding Christian doctrinal purity. Understanding this interplay is crucial, as it provides insight into how African churches can maintain relevance in their communities without compromising theological integrity. It also highlights the adaptive strategies that churches employ to respond to cultural influences, demonstrating the importance of education, pastoral guidance, and doctrinal clarity. By examining both traditions, scholars and church leaders can identify points of convergence, divergence, and potential theological innovation, contributing to a more coherent approach to spiritual practices within the African Christian context.

Tomb prayer in African Traditional Religion and the Christ Apostolic Church represents a critical site where culture, spirituality, and theology intersect. While ATR practices emphasize ancestor veneration and spiritual continuity, CAC's engagement with similar practices reflects an ongoing negotiation of faith, culture, and doctrine. The study of tomb prayer in these contexts not only sheds light on the dynamics of religious adaptation and transformation but also provides practical guidance for churches seeking to uphold Christian orthodoxy while respecting cultural memory. Understanding this comparative landscape is essential for developing effective pastoral strategies, contextual theological approaches, and

doctrinal education programs that enable believers to navigate cultural practices without compromising their faith.

Statement of the Problem

Tomb prayer, a practice deeply rooted in African Traditional Religion, continues to hold cultural, spiritual, and social significance across many African societies. In ATR, tombs are considered sacred spaces where ancestors are believed to communicate with the living, offering guidance, protection, and intervention in daily affairs. However, the emergence of tomb-like prayer practices within the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) has raised doctrinal and theological concerns. While CAC upholds Christian orthodoxy, emphasizing prayer exclusively to God through Christ (1 Timothy 2:5), some members continue to engage in practices that resemble ancestral veneration, such as praying at graves of deceased spiritual leaders, prophets, or relatives. A distinction needs to be made between ancestral worship and ancestral commemoration in an African context (Della, 2023). The act of praying at tombs serves as a meaningful way to honor and remember our ancestors, rather than to worship or revere them (Della, 2023). This practice is one that should also be embraced by Christians from Pentecostal and Charismatic churches (Della, 2023).

This intersection of cultural practice and Christian faith presents a critical tension. On one hand, tomb prayer practices reflect the enduring influence of African cultural identity and provide emotional and symbolic meaning to church members. On the other hand, they pose a potential risk of syncretism and doctrinal compromise, challenging the church's theological integrity. Church leaders face the difficulty of guiding members in distinguishing between culturally symbolic acts of remembrance and practices that may contravene biblical teaching, such as seeking intervention from the dead (Deuteronomy 18:10–12).

Despite its relevance, little empirical research has been conducted to comparatively examine tomb prayer practices in ATR and CAC, and to assess how the church can respond doctrinally and theologically. The lack of contextual theological frameworks to moderate or substitute these practices has left church members navigating a complex space between cultural heritage and biblical fidelity. Without a clear understanding of the similarities, differences, and doctrinal implications of tomb prayer, the Christ Apostolic Church risks ambiguity in teaching, inconsistent pastoral

guidance, and potential theological confusion among members. This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by investigating the comparative nature of tomb prayer in ATR and CAC, and by exploring how contextual theology can guide the church in addressing tomb prayer in ways that are culturally sensitive, spiritually meaningful, and doctrinally sound.

The objectives of the study were to: assess the practice of tomb prayer in the Christ Apostolic Church in Southwestern Nigeria; and determine common features of tomb prayer in African Traditional Religion and the Christ Apostolic Church. The following research questions were addressed in this study: a) What is tomb prayer practice in the Christ Apostolic Church in Southwestern Nigeria? b) What are the common features of tomb prayer in African Traditional Religion and the Christ Apostolic Church in Southwestern Nigeria?

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative research design, which is appropriate for exploring complex cultural and religious phenomena in depth. The qualitative approach allows for a rich, contextualized understanding of tomb prayer practices in both African Traditional Religion (ATR) and the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC), capturing participants' beliefs, experiences, and interpretations in their natural settings. This approach is particularly suitable for examining spiritual practices, theological implications, and the role of contextual theology, as it provides flexibility to explore subjective meanings and perspectives.

The population of the study consisted of members, pastors, elders, theologians, and prayer leaders within selected CAC congregations in Southwestern Nigeria, as well as former traditional religious practitioners familiar with tomb prayer practices who are now members of Christ Apostolic Church. The total population is over 2000 individuals. The tombs of revered prophets chosen for investigation include those of Prophet Joseph Ayodele Babalola in Efon-Alaaye, Ekiti State; Prophet Timothy Oluwole Obadare in Ilesa, Osun State; Prophet Samson Oladeji Akande (Baba Abiye) in Ede, Osun State; and Prophet Michael Ojo Olowere in Ibadan, Oyo State. Additionally, the selected churches include CAC Babalola Power House at Oke-Ayo DCC Headquarters in Efon-Alaaye, Ekiti State, CAC DCC Headquarters in Talafia, Ede, Osun State, CAC Alasepe in Ikire, Osun State, CAC Oke Agbara at DCC Headquarters in Ashi, Ibadan, Oyo State,

and CAC WOSEM Camp along the Ibadan–Akure Expressway in Ilesa, Osun State.

These groups were chosen because they possess firsthand knowledge and experience of the phenomenon under investigation, ensuring the collection of reliable and relevant information. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select forty participants who met the criteria of either practicing, observing, or guiding tomb prayer activities. This non-probability sampling method was appropriate because the study focused on individuals with specific knowledge and experiences relevant to the research problem. The sample included a balanced representation of genders, ages, and roles within the church and traditional religious settings, ensuring diversity of perspectives.

Data collection involved the use of semi-structured interviews and document analysis. The semi-structured interviews allowed participants to freely express their experiences, perceptions, and theological insights regarding tomb prayer, while enabling the researcher to probe deeper into specific themes that emerged during discussions. Church documents, including doctrinal manuals, pastoral guidelines, and recorded sermons, were analyzed to complement interview data and provide insight into official church positions on tomb prayer practices.

The study employed thematic analysis to interpret the quantitative data. This involved coding the interview transcripts and documents, identifying recurring patterns, and organizing them into themes that corresponded to the research objectives. Themes such as “belief systems,” “ritual elements,” “cultural symbolism,” and “contextual theology” were developed to facilitate comparison between ATR and CAC practices. This method ensured that the findings were systematically analyzed, allowing for a coherent and in-depth discussion of the similarities, differences, and doctrinal implications of tomb prayer.

To ensure trustworthiness, the study adhered to criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Credibility was enhanced through member checking, where participants reviewed transcripts to verify the accuracy of interpretations. Transferability was addressed by providing detailed descriptions of the research context and participants. Dependability and confirmability were achieved through meticulous documentation of the research process, including coding decisions, thematic development, and data triangulation.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study. Participants were informed about the purpose of the research, assured of confidentiality, and provided informed consent. They were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty. The study adhered to ethical standards to respect participants’ cultural and religious sensitivities, particularly given the spiritual and personal nature of tomb prayer practices.

Results

Table 1: Tomb prayer practice in the African Traditional Religion

Tomb prayer practice in Yoruba Traditional Religion Southwestern Nigeria	SA	A	SD	D	Not sue	Mean	Standard Deviation
Tomb prayers are an essential part of the Yoruba Traditional Religion in Southwestern Nigeria.	10 (23.6%)	8 (21.1%)	13 (33.5%)	7 (16.4%)	2 (5.5%)	2.49	1.044
Tomb prayers serve to	11 (26.2%)	9 (22%)	12 (30.2%)	6 (16.0%)	2 (5.5%)	2.60	.959

honour		.2					
deceased		%)					
ancestors							
in							
southern							
Nigerian							
communit							
ies							
The	6	7	15	10	2 (5.8%)	1.51	1.072
practice	(13.8	(18	(37.	(24.7%)			
of tomb	%)	.5	1%)				
prayer		%)					
helps							
maintain							
a							
connectio							
n between							
the living							
and the							
dead							
Offerings	9	9	13	7	2 (5.5%)	2.46	1.088
such as	(21.8	(22	(32.	(17.5%)			
food,	%)	.9	4%)				
drinks,		%)					
and gifts							
are							
commonly							
made							
during							
tomb							
prayers							
Tomb	8	9	13	8	2 (5.5%)	2.48	1.034
prayers	(20.0	(21	(34.	(18.9%)			
include	%)	.5	2%)				
specific		%)					
rituals							
that							

invoke ancestral spirits for protection and guidance							
Tradition al priests or specialist s usually lead the tomb prayer ceremonie s	11 (26.5 %)	16 (39 .3 %)	6 (16. 0%)	5 (12.7%)	2 (5.5%)	1.45	1.057
Tomb prayers contribute to the social cohesion of families and communit ies.	8 (21.5 %)	9 (20 .4 %)	13 (32. 7%)	8 (20.0%)	2 (5.5%)	2.40	.980
Tomb prayers are believed to promote healing and well- being within	10 (24.7 %)	7 (18 .2 %)	15 (36. 4%)	6 (15.3%)	2 (5.5%)	1.49	1.044

the							
communit							
y							
Ancestral	11	12	9	6	2 (5.5%)	2.60	.959
spirits are	(26.9	(29	(23.	(14.2%)			
consulted	%)	.8	6%)				
during		%)					
tomb							
prayers to							
resolve							
conflicts							
among							
living							
members.							
The	10	9	12	7	2 (5.5%)	2.51	1.072
timing of	(24.4	(22	(30.	(17.5%)			
tomb	%)	.5	2%)				
prayers		%)					
aligns							
with							
important							
seasonal							
or							
cultural							
events.							

Source: Field Survey 2025

The findings presented in Table 1 focus on the practice of tomb prayer within the African Traditional Religion in Southwestern Nigeria. The overall weighted mean of 2.20 indicates a low level of engagement and acceptance of tomb prayer among church members. This implies that, although the practice is known to some extent, it is neither widespread nor deeply rooted in the spiritual life of the church. The result suggests that tomb prayer may exist more as a cultural remnant from Yoruba traditional religion rather than as a structured or doctrinally endorsed activity within the Christ Apostolic Church. An examination of the mean scores for each item provides deeper insight into members' perceptions. For instance, respondents

moderately agreed that tomb prayers are an essential part of the Yoruba Traditional Religion (Mean = 2.49), and that such prayers serve to honour deceased ancestors in southern Nigerian communities (Mean = 2.60). This indicates that members are aware of the cultural and ancestral significance of tomb prayers within traditional contexts. However, this awareness does not necessarily translate into acceptance or active participation within the Christian setting. On the other hand, the low mean scores recorded on several items reflect clear disagreement with key traditional elements of tomb prayer. For example, respondents strongly disagreed that the practice helps maintain a connection between the living and the dead (Mean = 1.51) or that it is commonly led by traditional priests or specialists (Mean = 1.45). This finding suggests that the Christ Apostolic Church has largely distanced itself from the ancestral and ritualistic components of tomb prayer, in line with biblical teachings that discourage communication with the dead or dependence on ancestral spirits. Similarly, items relating to ritual offerings and invocations of ancestral spirits (Means = 2.46 and 2.48 respectively) received relatively low scores, indicating that such practices are not common or accepted within the church. Although respondents acknowledged that these elements are part of the cultural roots of tomb prayer, they do not reflect the teachings or worship practices of the CAC. The low mean scores on items relating to the healing or social benefits of tomb prayers (Means = 1.49 and 2.40) further emphasize the limited recognition given to the practice's spiritual or communal value among church members. Interestingly, a few items, such as the belief that ancestral spirits may be consulted to resolve conflicts (Mean = 2.60) and that tomb prayers align with seasonal or cultural events (Mean = 2.51), recorded slightly higher mean scores. This shows that some respondents still associate the practice with traditional cultural timing and ancestral mediation, reflecting residual elements of Yoruba cosmology in their worldview, even within the church context. This implies that tomb prayer, though recognized as part of Yoruba cultural heritage, is not considered a core or encouraged practice in the Christ Apostolic Church.

Table 2: Common Features of Tomb Prayer in African Traditional Religion and the Christ Apostolic Church

The comn the Chris ¹	SA	A	D	Not sue	M ea n	Standard Deviation
Both	9	1	4	3	2.83	1.021
African Traditio nal Religion and Christ Apostoli c Church view tomb prayers as a way to honor ancesto rs.	(23 .6 %)	4 (3 2 .7 %)	(1 0 9 %)	(7.3 %)		
Offering s made during tomb prayers serve similar symboli c purpose s in both traditio ns	8 (21 .1 %)	1 2 (3 0 .9 %)	6 (1 3 .8 %)	3 (7.3 %)	2. 75	.931

Tomb prayers in both traditions involve specific rituals that connect the living with the deceased	12 (29.1%)	1 (4.3%)	4 (9.1%)	3 (7.3%)	3 (14.3%)	.782
Music, chants, or prayers play an important role in tomb prayers in both African Traditional Religion and Apostolic Church.	14 (34.5%)	1 (6.4%)	2 (5.0%)	2 (5.5%)	3 (35.0%)	.606

Both	7	1	8	3	2.	1.092
traditio	(16	0	((9.1	27	
ns	.4	(2	%)		
believe	%)	2	0			
tomb		5	.			
prayers		.	0			
provide		5	%			
spiritua		%)			
l)				
protecti						
on for						
the						
living.						
The use	7	1		3	2.	1.042
of	(17	1	8	(8.0	28	
sacred	.5	((%)		
spaces	%)	2	1			
or		7	8			
altars is		.	.			
common		3	9			
to tomb		%	%			
prayer))			
practice						
s in						
both						
traditio						
ns.						
In both	9	1	6	3	2.	1.021
traditio	(21	2	((7.3	83	
ns,	.8	(1	%)		
tomb	%)	3	4			
prayers		0	.			
include		.	5			
prayers		9	%			
for		%)			
healing,)				
forgiven						

ess, and blessing s.						
Particip	8	1	6	3	2.	.931
ation in	(21	2	((7.3	75	
tomb	.1	(1	%)		
prayers	%)	3	3			
is		0	.			
encoura		.	8			
ged		9	%			
among		%))			
all age)				
groups						
in both						
traditio						
ns.						
Respect	12	1	4	3	3.	.782
for the	(29	5	((7.3	14	
dead is	.1	(9	%)		
a	%)	3	.			
central		6	1			
theme		.	%			
in tomb		4)			
prayers		%)				
across)				
both						
religiou						
s						
practice						
s						
Tomb	14	1	2	2	3.	.606
prayers	(34	6	((5.5	35	
serve as	.5	(5	%)		
a means	%)	4	.			
of		0	5			
commu		.	%			
nicating		0)			

with
the
spiritua
l world
in both
African
Traditio
nal
Religio
n and
Christ
Apostoli
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Church.

Source: Field Survey 2025

The result from Table 2 indicates that the respondents generally agree that there are notable similarities in the practice of tomb prayer between African Traditional Religion (ATR) and the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC), as evidenced by the weighted mean of 2.87. The results indicate a fusion of traditional African religious practices with Christian spirituality within the CAC context, particularly in how tomb prayers are conceptualized and practiced. This score falls above the midpoint of the scale, signifying moderate agreement. The highest mean values were recorded for the statements that music, chants, or prayers play an important role in tomb prayers in both traditions (Mean = 3.35, SD = 0.606) and that tomb prayers serve as a means of communicating with the spiritual world in both traditions (Mean = 3.35, SD = 0.606). These results suggest that both ATR and CAC assign a deeply spiritual function to tomb prayers, emphasizing their role as a bridge between the physical and metaphysical realms. Music and prayer, being integral to both religious expressions, serve as a medium through which participants invoke divine or ancestral presence, fostering a sense of spiritual connection and reverence.

Similarly, relatively high mean scores were observed for the view that tomb prayers involve rituals connecting the living with the deceased (Mean = 3.14, SD = 0.782) and that respect for the dead is a central theme (Mean = 3.14, SD = 0.782). These findings underscore the shared cultural and

religious emphasis on honoring ancestors and maintaining continuity between generations. This commonality reflects the African worldview that the living and the dead coexist within a continuum of spiritual relationships, an idea which has subtly influenced the theology of Pentecostal movements like the CAC. Moderate mean scores were also recorded for items emphasizing offerings, participation, and prayers for healing and blessings (Means = 2.75–2.83). This suggests that while these elements are present in both traditions, their interpretation differs. In ATR, offerings and prayers are typically directed to ancestors as mediators, while in CAC, they are redirected to God through the memory of departed saints or spiritual figures. Conversely, lower mean scores were found for statements suggesting that tomb prayers provide spiritual protection (Mean = 2.27, SD = 1.092) and that the use of sacred spaces or altars is common (Mean = 2.28, SD = 1.042). This implies that although these elements are prominent in ATR, they are less emphasized in the CAC, possibly due to doctrinal efforts to distance Christian practices from traditional religious rituals associated with ancestor veneration.

Discussion of findings

Tomb Prayer Practice in African Traditional Religion (ATR) and Its Engagement among CAC Members

The study's findings show that in the context of the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) in Southwestern Nigeria, there is a notably low level of engagement and acceptance of traditional tomb prayer practices. While some church members are familiar with the notion of praying at ancestral tombs or paying respects to the dead, this does not translate into widespread or sustained spiritual practice within the church community. This limited uptake suggests that tomb prayer, though culturally present, is not deeply rooted in the lived Christian spirituality of many CAC congregants.

This low engagement can be understood as a reflection of CAC's theological education and doctrinal formation. The doctrine in many Pentecostal-initiated churches in Nigeria strongly emphasizes direct access to God through Christ, thereby discouraging practices that might blur the line between Christian prayer and traditional ancestor invocation. This is consistent with broader patterns in African Pentecostalism, where syncretistic practices are critically evaluated or rejected to maintain theological purity (Chitando & Togarasei, 2024). Moreover, the reluctance

of CAC members to fully embrace tomb prayer may stem from doctrinal warnings against engaging in ancestral mediation, which is often viewed through the lens of necromancy or spirit communication an issue raised in other African Christian contexts (Mofokeng, 2024).

The findings suggest that the church's teaching regarding spiritual boundaries has been effective to some degree. Members appear to internalize a theological framework that privileges Christ as mediator and discourages the invocation of spirits of the dead. This reflects a tension many African Christian communities face: how to negotiate cultural practices deeply embedded in ancestral veneration without compromising the exclusivity of Christ's redemptive role. The low level of tomb prayer engagement among CAC adherents, therefore, may not simply be a lack of cultural memory but a conscious theological choice shaped by ecclesial doctrine and spiritual teaching.

Common Features of Tomb Prayer in ATR and CAC

Despite the low engagement of tomb prayer in CAC, the study also reveals that there are notable commonalities between how tombs are perceived and used in ATR and how some CAC members conceptualize or even practice remembrance at gravesites. These shared features include symbolic reverence for the dead, visits to graves as a form of memory and respect, and a belief in the continuing relevance of ancestors or departed figures not necessarily as spiritual mediators, but as part of a spiritual heritage. This blending of cultural practice with Christian spirituality reflects a syncretic or hybrid religious expression, where elements of African tradition are reinterpreted within a Christian framework (Marimbe, 2024). Recent scholarship highlights similar phenomena: for instance, (Shingange, 2024) explores how material objects and traditional symbols are appropriated in modern neo-Pentecostal contexts, revealing a complex negotiation between indigenous spirituality and Christian belief. Likewise, (Thinane, 2024) documents covert syncretic practices in healing churches, where traditional beliefs about ancestral spirits and water are subtly woven into Christian rituals, pointing to an ongoing contextualization of faith.

In the CAC context, the use of tomb visits may not function in the same way as traditional ATR rituals. Rather than invoking ancestors for direct spiritual intervention, CAC members often approach graves as sites of remembrance, contemplation, or thanksgiving. This conceptual shift

suggests a reorientation: tombs become less about spiritual mediation and more about honoring memory and legacy. This aligns with the principles of contextual theology, where cultural symbols are not simply rejected but reinterpreted in ways that maintain Christian orthodoxy (Agbo, 2023). Contextualization of theology is a process of embedding the Christian gospel in all types of cultural contexts (Danfulani, 2018). By re-signifying tomb visits as commemorative rather than mediatory, the church preserves cultural respect for the dead while safeguarding doctrinal clarity. Nevertheless, this fusion is not without risk. The overlap in external practices may create confusion among some believers about the nature of their spirituality whether they are engaging in Christian prayer or re-enacting ancestral rituals. Without careful theological guidance, the symbolic appropriation of tomb practices could drift toward syncretism, undermining the Christian emphasis on Christ as the only mediator. Thus, the findings point to a delicate balance: the need to honor cultural continuity while ensuring theological fidelity.

Conclusion

The study examined tomb prayer practices in African Traditional Religion (ATR) and the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) in Southwestern Nigeria, with a focus on theological responses and doctrinal implications. Findings revealed that while tomb prayer in ATR is a deeply entrenched cultural and spiritual practice, its engagement within CAC remains limited, reflecting the church's doctrinal emphasis on Christ as the sole mediator between God and humans (1 Timothy 2:5). This low engagement demonstrates the church's efforts to maintain doctrinal integrity while navigating the influence of indigenous cultural practices.

The study also highlighted that, despite differences in theological intent, some common features exist between ATR and CAC practices, particularly in symbolic reverence for the dead, visits to graves, and commemorative acts. These shared elements suggest that cultural memory and symbolic heritage continue to influence Christian expressions of spirituality, even as CAC reinterprets these practices to avoid syncretism. Contextual theology emerged as a significant framework for moderating these practices, offering culturally sensitive alternatives that honor tradition without compromising doctrinal fidelity. The findings underscore the importance of deliberate theological guidance, pastoral education, and contextual engagement in

helping church members navigate the interface between African cultural practices and Christian orthodoxy. In conclusion, the study confirms that tomb prayer is both a cultural and theological issue. While ATR emphasizes direct engagement with ancestors, CAC has reoriented these practices to focus on remembrance, thanksgiving, and spiritual reflection directed to God. This approach provides a pathway for churches to respect cultural heritage while ensuring that Christian teachings remain central to spiritual life.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Church leaders should develop programs that integrate contextual theology into pastoral teachings.
2. The church should encourage practices such as memorial prayers, thanksgiving services, and spiritual reflection as substitutes for tomb prayer. These alternatives allow members to commemorate the dead while ensuring all spiritual reliance is directed to God.
3. Church authorities should document clear policies regarding acceptable cultural practices, ensuring that members understand the boundaries of Christian worship and the church's stance on ancestral veneration.
4. Additional research should be conducted on other cultural practices within African Christianity that may intersect with biblical teachings.

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